

Development of **Flame Retardant Green Composites** by Hybrid Flame Retardant Approach

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1. INTRODUCTION

Natural Fiber Composites - Scenario

Initial stage

Less importance, demand & awareness

Flax + Phenolic Fuselage skins of spitfires 1939	Hemp Prototype car by Henry Ford 1942	Cotton + PE Body of "Trabant" car in Germany 1950-90
Clay/Straw reinforced composites 1500 BC	Composite bow 1200 AD	Parkesine – 1st synthetic resin 1870's

Propagation stage

Slowly started for commercial applications

Flax, Hemp Number of automotive applications 2000~	Kenaf + PLA Cases of cellular phones 2004~	Flax, Hemp Kenaf Sporting Good 2006~	Hemp, Kenaf Thermal and acoustic insulation panel 2010~
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Number of article published on Natural Fiber Composites (NFC), Green Composites and Fire Retardancy of NFC in Elsevier journals. www.sciencedirect.com (December 2022)

Year	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Articles	1152	1204	1209	1341	1539	1857	2019	2232	2429	2525	2578	3173	3609	4392	4678	5427	6222	7542	8127	9678	11510	14813	17624

Present scenario

Slowly emerging for commercial applications

Motorsports 17624	Skin & Sporting 14813
Furniture & Interior 11510	Automotive interior 9678

Number of article published on Natural Fiber Composites (NFC), Green Composites and Fire Retardancy of NFC in Elsevier journals. www.sciencedirect.com (December 2022)

1. INTRODUCTION

NFCs - Limitations

While natural fibers offer a sustainable and renewable alternative to carbon or glass fiber, the composites industry has been slow to adopt them due to various challenges.

Limitations: Main stages of Natural fibers – Natural Fiber Composites

Limitations - Natural Fiber Composites – Commercialization

J. Marine Science and Engineering 2023, 11, 1076

- ✓ Limited supply and Variable fiber quality
- ✓ Limited mechanical strength in finished parts
- ✓ Differences in manufacturability and depending on the material
- ✓ Higher material cost compared with fiber glass

Keen Issues – Current Research Focus

- ✓ Thermally weak and sensitive to flame
- ✓ Mechanical stability in the presence of FR additives

1. INTRODUCTION

NFCs – Developments & Objectives

Fabrication of **flame resistant Bio-composites**

2. EXPERIMENTAL & METHODOLOGY

Reinforcement: Flax fibers

Cellulose Structure

- ✓ Cellulose: 70 - 75%
- ✓ Lignin: 4 - 4.5%

Properties

Fibers	E-glass	Flax	Hemp	Jute	Kenaf
Density (kg/m ³)	2550	1530	1520	1520	1193
E-modulus (GPa)	71	58±15	60	60	14-38
Tensile strength (MPa)	3400	1339	920	860	240
Elongation at break (%)	3.4	3.27	1.7	2	-

Materials (Basel) 6(11), 5171, 2013

Advantages

- ✓ Better Mechanical Properties
- ✓ Water absorption in small (7%)
- ✓ Flax fiber has a structure which can be compared to a composite material composed of helical cellulose fibrils embedded in a matrix of polymer (hemi-cellulose, lignin and pectin)

relative specific flexural stiffness [-]

Aluminium glass fibre composite carbon fibre composite flax fibre composite

Increased Damping properties by 250 %
Specific stiffness by 250 %

Bcomp power ribs
↑ increasing rib thickness

www.BCOMP.CH

Dis-Advantages

- ✓ **Flammable**
- ✓ Dimensional instability
- ✓ High moisture absorption
- ✓ Anisotropic behavior
- ✓ Limited processing temp.
- ✓ Fungal attack and microbial

Low Limited Oxygen Index

	LOI	HRR
PP/Kenaf	19	700 kW/m ²
PP/Flax	21.6	731 kW/m ²
Epoxy/Flax	21.3	709 kW/m ²

Composites Science Technology 162,2018

Flax Fabric

2. EXPERIMENTAL & METHODOLOGY

Matrix: Vinyl ester

Structure

Properties

Property	Polyester	Vinyl ester	Epoxy
Density (g/cm ³)	1.2-1.5	1.2-1.4	1.1-1.4
Tensile strength (MPa)	40-90	69-83	35-100
Elastic Modulus (GPa)	2-4.5	3.1-3.8	3-6
Elongation (%)	2	4-7	1-6
Izode impact strength (J/m)	0.15-3.2	2.5	0.3
Compressive strength (MPa)	90-250	100	100-200
Water absorption (24h @ 20 °c)	0.1-0.3	0.1	0.1-0.4
Cure shrinkage (%)	4-8	N/A	1-2

Composites: Part B 56, 296, 2014

Advantages

- ✓ Most of the properties of Vinyl ester are intermediate between Polyesters and Epoxies
- ✓ Some of the most important properties are:
 - Water and chemical resistance
 - Electrical Stability
 - Thermal stability
 - Toughness
 - Low volatiles during manufacture
 - Low shrinkage
 - Average cost

Literature

Dis-Advantages

- ✓ High shrinkage
- ✓ **Poor fire resistance**
- ✓ Higher cost than polyester

Vinyl ester panel

2. EXPERIMENTAL & METHODOLOGY

Flame Retardants: CS, APP & NCSAPP

Chitosan (CS)

Ammonium Polyphosphate (APP)

Novel Flame Retardant (NCSAPP)

The synthesized **NCSAPP** was found to exhibit **superior fire retardant** properties than CS and APP.

2. EXPERIMENTAL & METHODOLOGY

Manufacturing of Vinyl ester/Flax fabric

Surface modification of Flax Fibers

VARTM process

Modified Flax Fiber

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

APP treated FF – Surface Morphology & X-RD

Surface Morphology

Flax fibres

10%APP treated Flax fibres

Alkali treated Flax fibres

15%APP treated Flax fibres

5%APP treated Flax fibres

20%APP treated Flax fibres

X-ray patterns

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

APP treated FF – Thermal & Flame retardancy

FRs loaded Vinyl Ester/Flax Fiber Composites

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

FRs-VE/FF Composite – Thermal & Flame retardancy

FRs loaded Vinyl Ester/Modified Flax Fiber Composites

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

FRs-VE/mFF Composites– Thermal & Flame resistance

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

FRs-VE/mFF Composites– Flame resistance

Sample	VFT		Cone calorimeter				
	Air		Air				
	Rank	pHRR [KW/m ²]	THR [MJ/m ²]	TSR [m ² /m]	CO ₂ P [g/s]	CO P [g/s]	SPR [m ² /s]
VE/mFF	V0	1659	248.7	10882	0.84	0.068	0.67
CS-VE/mFF	V0	483	33.1	1212	0.29	0.027	0.20
APP-VE/mFF	V0	493	53.8	2633	0.17	0.017	0.22
NCSAPP-VE/mFF	V0	503	28.6	1421	0.26	0.025	0.20

3. RESULTS & DISCUSSION

FRs-VE/mFF Composite – Tensile & Flexural Behavior

Tensile behavior

Flexural behavior

- ✓ The porosity of the fibers was reduced owing to the settlement of the APP between the gaps of the woven folds.
- ✓ The change in the fiber surface reduced the interaction between the resin and the fibers, thereby reducing the strength of the pure and FR-filled composites.
- ✓ Generally, the compatibility of the additives with a matrix/reinforcement determines the mechanical properties of the composite. An additional advantage of this approach is that a single compound can be used for the additive and surface treatment.

4. CONCLUSIONS

VE/FF Composites – Application area

Flame resistance

HRR 69%
THR 78%
SPR 75%
CO₂P 65%
COP 60%

Mechanical strength

TS 10%
TM 18%
FS 14%
FM 24%

Probable application area

Outdoor high temperature technical products

Sub-structural components

VE/FF Composites

- **Flame resistant** Vinyl ester/**Flax fiber composites** are manufactured hybrid approach.
 - ✓ The APP-modified **FF exhibited** excellent **thermal stability** (38% residue at 700 °C) and **flame retardancy** (UL94-V0 and HRR-77.64 w/g).
 - ✓ VE/**modified FF and FRs** filled VE/**modified FF composites** exhibited significantly higher **thermal stability** owing to the formation of ~28% char residue at 700 °C and flame retardancy by reaching V0 rank in UL94, as well as **fire extinguishing** immediately after removal of the fire source.
 - ✓ The NCSAPP filled VE/modified FF composite showed reasonably better mechanical properties.
- Over all, this investigation provides design for sub-structural components for outdoor engineering applications.

Research Center

Center for Advanced Material Research

Core Competences

Green Bio-composites

Bio-waste additives

3D printing & Analysis

Self-healing systems

Flame retardant composites

Research crew

Group 1 Manufacturing and testing	Group 2 Coating	Group 3 Structural Analysis
 Prof. Young-ung Jung		

Support Organization	Research Title	Period	Research fund (USD)
	Flame resistant Eco-hybrid Composites	2018/06-2027/02	5 million

Research professors

 Dr. Zeeshan				
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Students

 Phuong								
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Research Center – Natural Fiber Products

Enough strength
for small scale
wind turbine

Lightweight

Sound absorption

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

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THANK YOU
— For your attention —

ACSD 첨단복합재료 및
구조설계 실험실
Advanced Composites
& Structural Design Lab.

CAMR

Center for Advanced Materials Research

